

Academic Management Primer Diptych

notes from the front line of art-science crossover education

Adrian Lenardic and Anthony Covington

Panel 01: How To Cut Departments You Want Gone and Come Out Blame-Free

Triumph Over Mastery – Mark Tansey

Essay 01 provides a model that allows university executive leadership to cut the fat and come out golden in the public eye.

Panel 02: All BIS Are Equal, Buts Some Are More Equal Than Others

Vintage Poster Modified by Authors

Essay 02 provides a means for university leadership to increase their cash flow by providing clients with the enhanced educational experiences they deserve.

Academic Management Primer I: How to Cut Unwanted Departments and Come Out Blame Free

notes from the front line of art-science crossover education

Adrian Lenardic, Rice Univ.; Anthony Covington, esq., 1-800-UCiteMe.

Let's say you are a part of executive leadership at a university of higher education. You and your colleagues have noticed that some departments just aren't bringing in the cash. You want them gone but they are departments that have some level of support, be it from donors who want to see the "classics" of liberal arts education stay in the curricula or from those who want to keep departments that are built around the idea of enhanced diversity. If you shut them down, you run the risk of looking like a meanie. That's not good for public relations. You need a way to make the departments go away without looking like the bad guy. You need to make it seem like the departments themselves are to blame. You need to make it seem that the departments have not stepped up to serve student needs.

You already know that the departments you want gone have smaller class sizes than your cash cow departments [1]. In a light-bulb moment you think 'If we set a minimum class size, we can have our cake and eat it too'. A minimum number of student clients taking classes from any department will be seen as a measure of whether the department is serving student needs. If some departments fall below, then the public and your donors can't blame you for having to cut them. They aren't stepping up. You even gave them a chance by setting a minimum number and had they not been lazy they could have hit that number. You come out golden.

Just one last thing: How to set the number. You could just pick one but that's risky, What if it's too low? Those pesky departments may hit the number. If you set it too high, then it could look like you are loading the dice. You need to set a minimum number that is right at the level that the departments you want gone could never hit (or, at least, could not all hit, so you would still be able to cut a bunch of them; a good start for an executive leader [2]). What you need is a model [3].

Models begin with a purpose [4]. Your purpose is to determine a number subject to constraints. Let's call it the magic number and give it the symbol M . The number represents how many students, on average, need to take classes from a department to justify the departments continued existence. The constraints are: 1) To the outside world, the number needs to appear fair and achievable for all departments; and 2) The number needs to be unachievable by departments that need to go. That sets the model goal - the output you seek is the magic number M .

The next step is to ask what the output depends on. Here is a list:

N: The number of students at your university

Dw: The number of departments you want to keep

Dl: The number of departments you want gone

Cw: The number of classes offered per semester by keep 'em departments

Cl: The number of classes offered per semester by loose 'em departments

T: The total number of classes any student takes per semester

Pr: A popularity ratio that expresses the ratio of majors in Dw versus Dl

The popularity ratio, Pr , is something executive leadership can control during admissions. Simply admit more students who declare majors in your Dw departments. You can also promote your Dw departments during student orientations as the ones that provide the best student outcomes in terms of higher paying jobs and financial mobility. Students will preferentially take more classes in their majors [5]. This allows us to assume that Pr will be a good measure of the ratio of students taking classes from Dw versus Dl .

We are now ready to construct the model. The availability of students to take classes in a semester will be:

$$N \times T.$$

The number of students taking classes from your slacker departments, if they could hit your magic number M , would be:

$$Cl \times Dl \times M.$$

The number of students taking classes from your productive departments, noting that the numbers will be a factor of Pr above the slacker departments, would be:

$$Cw \times Dw \times Pr \times M.$$

We can now determine the highest M value your Dl departments could, on average, possibly hit. The model gives us:

$$M = (N \times T) / (Cl \times Dl + Cw \times Dw \times Pr).$$

Let's run through an example. Assume the following values:

$$N = 5000$$

$$Dw = 30$$

$$Dl = 20$$

$$Cw = 10$$

$$Cl = 10$$

$$T = 4$$

$$Pr = 3$$

With those values, your magic number is 18. So, to set the scheme in motion you announce that all departments must, on average, have 20 students in the classes they offer per semester [6]. That is hardly unreasonable. If a department can't hit that fair and (seemingly) achievable number, then it's not serving student clientele and you have no choice but to cut the department. But wait, that's only step one.

On to step two of the scheme.

Some of your slacker departments might hit $M=20$ but it will be impossible for all of them to. Let's say that allows you to cut half of them (with no blame placed on executive leadership as the departments simply could not pass a reasonable bar). It would be a waste of facilities to cut some departments and not allow others to grow – after all you have cleared out some space, and it was wasted space at that [7].

So, you grow your Dw departments such that each can now offer 12 classes per semester [8]. Using the example numbers, the maximum your Dl departments can hit, even with less of them, is 17 students on average in the classes they offer per semester. To the public and your donors, it will be clear those departments are doing even worse than before [9]. You even gave them added time to show they could step up and they chose not to. Clearly, they are to blame. You have no choice but to cut them.

Your *DI* departments are financial-drags on your university, but they may have a clever person or two within them. They may see strategies that could allow them to hit your newly imposed expectations. Maybe they choose to downsize so they have less classes, which could make it easier to clear your *M* requirement. Maybe they have one or two faculty members who can draw large class numbers so that one large class offsets their other classes. No worries. Our model has it covered.

The big popular class strategy runs into a practical limit. Universities do not have infinite space so class sizes will be limited by facilities restrictions, which are different for different departments and can be adjusted over time (e.g., if a department is dropping in numbers, then its facilities should clearly be reduced to minimize wasted space). All you need to do is limit facilities and space on the departments that did not hit your initial *M* requirement. That will be fully justified as your preforming departments should be rewarded with more space and space is finite.

The downsize strategy also runs into a practical limit based on the definition of a department. The number of classes a department offers is proportional to the number of faculty within a department [8]. Clearly a 'department of one' is not a department. Is a department of three a department? Arguable. Who can make that decision? Whose job is it to make the decision? Well, that's clearly part of the duties assigned to executive leadership. This adds the following to our model:

Cm: The minimum number of classes a department must offer to be a department
Our main model equation allows you to set that number in a way that will not allow most of your *DI* departments to survive by progressive downsizing.

If some departments do hold on via downsizing, you can turn that to your advantage. It makes sense to group them into a single department (they are shrinking out of existence anyway). That new department will satisfy any remaining whiners who hold to the idea that a liberal arts education should go beyond vocational training. Just point them to your department of art-philosophy-ethics-history-classics-literature-ethnostudies. That will also satisfy customers who want to be at an ivy league-esq university that offers the 'classics' and ranking agencies will be able to check off the 'well rounded education' box. Win-win. Time to move on to making tenure a thing of the past and developing plans on how AI can replace some faculty and staff in your *Dw* departments - they can't all be winners [10].

The Triumph Over Mastery – Mark Tansey

The Triumph Over Mastery II – Mark Tansey

Notes and References

- [1] Your productive departments are the ones that generate commercial profits for your university from marketing their research products. They are the ones that can connect to corporations and/or start-ups to increase the financial footprint of your university. They are the departments that executive leadership promotes as offering students the skills they need to go get well paid jobs (your students deserve the highest paid jobs – maybe even executive leadership positions). These are the departments that ranking organizations (e.g., US News and World Report) score high on student outcomes and income mobility metrics. The ones touted as offering financially desirable majors. That sort of recognition – that attention – is a cash equivalent in the attention economy.
- [2] If you happen to be at a university that still refers to administration as ‘administration’ and to those who work in administration as ‘administrators’, then you need to correct that. The new way to speak about administration is to refer to it as executive leadership. In keeping with the new speak, all the vice presidents, assistant vice presidents, provosts, vice provosts, assistant vice provosts, deans, deanettes, etc. are each spoken of as an executive leader. Titles matter – they have historically set a necessary level of hierarchy and respect – so choose your titles wisely. If you like, you can also use the title of ‘thought leader’ on your webpages. Those who are not leaders are followers (e.g., faculty and staff). You and your executive leadership colleagues know this but in public its best to refer to non-leaders as ‘your team’ (even though leadership runs the university, you still need workers and followers to make a university run so best not to alienate them until you cut them loose).

- [3] You could also go to a consulting firm that specializes in ‘efficiency’ and have them do a multi-year study of your university to reach the conclusion you want and help justify it (i.e., “Hey a prestigious consulting company reached the decision, it wasn’t our call.”). There are companies that specialize in those services. They will provide you with multi-page reports with graphs, projections, charts, and excessive details. If you go that route, cool – you will get the result you want. The thing is that you don’t need to pay those ridiculous fees and spend your valuable time reading reports and listening to presentations. Instead, consider our simple, cheaper, and less time-consuming scheme based on a quantitative model (btw: the authors teach scientific modeling at a prestigious university and have worked to help start-ups develop business plans using modeling methodologies – so, you know, credentials). At present, our modeling insights are offered free in this essay (although it will be paywalled soon).
- [4] Some consulting companies might also offer you models. To justify high fees, they may attach fancy names to them like AI Generated Strategy Scenarios. Don’t be fooled. These are, at their core, representations of some aspect of reality. Stated another way, they are models. Sure, one can feed model equations and associated assumptions into a computer and add sprinkles of artificial intelligence (AI), big data analytics (BDA) and machine learning (ML) to make it look like what’s offered is beyond the understanding of clients (so they are happy to pay the big money – abbreviations like AI, BDA and ML add to the mystique). Again, don’t be fooled. The core level is still the model equations and the model assumptions themselves. That’s the prize to keep your eye on. Our scheme is focused on that prize free of bells and whistles and ribbons and bows that make the model look like more than it is.
- [5] A rule of thumb is that if, for example, students take four classes per semester, then three of those, on average, will be related to their major. The other class will be part of what is often called “breadth requirements”. That falls under the idea that an education is not the same as vocational training and students should gain “general knowledge” – also referred to as a “a liberal arts education”. For a long time that antiquated idea has allowed your *DI* departments to drag your institution down. Even if those departments don’t have a lot of majors, they will argue that what they offer has value for educating future citizens – as opposed to just generating future workers. Executive leadership knows that’s naïve thinking in a neoliberal world. Yet, some donors and some of the public buys into that nonsense. That has allowed your *DI* departments to slide by without bringing sufficient financial return to your university. As our model will show, imposing proper expectations on these departments can put an end to that.
- [6] Make sure to connect this announcement to transformations being made at your university to enhance fairness and provide incentives for all departments to be their best selves. Those who see the incentives will increase their student numbers and those that don’t need to be penalized in the interest of transparency. Make it clear that transformations can’t be delayed. Create a sense of urgency – an urgency for all departments, faculty members and staff to deliver on the promise of your bold new transformation plan.
- [7] Herein lies another beauty of our model. There is no need to add any new facilities, space, or support. Our model creates a zero-sum competitive game amongst your departments. The departments that generate the most revenue gain at the expense of those that don’t. This competition is framed in terms of incentives and a transparency

[6]. Your department chairs will be eager to show that their departments want to step up and will not see the zero-sum nature of what's going on until it's too late. Academics are prone to wanting to be good university citizens and, as such, tend not to openly question leadership decisions (i.e., they want to be team players [2]). The internal competition our model initiates could even save you money – money that could, of course, be used to pave the way for enhanced executive leadership.

[8] The number of classes a department offers is proportional to the number of faculty within a department (all faculty need to teach at least one class a semester to justify a paycheck). Since you have cut some of your *DI* departments you need to make sure students have an adequate number of classes to choose from so you need to up your faculty numbers (and you have cleared some salary by sacking faculty from the *DI* departments that under-performed). It only makes sense that the high-flying departments, based on students served, should grow. Why would anyone grow the remaining *DI* departments that only barely cleared your reasonable *M* requirement? The example numbers highlight an added value of our model. For those numbers, you had to let 100 faculty go (it wasn't your choice, it was theirs). You replaced them with 60 new faculty. Clearly, executive leadership is being fiscally responsible in terms of new hires.

[9] In modeling terms, our scheme allows you to put your *DI* departments into a positive feedback loop. The more they try to take actions to fight an effect, the worse it gets. The loop nature will make it appear to the outside world that no one has manipulated the result – it's just the departments actions, or lack thereof, that are feeding back on the departments demise. Positive feedback loops allow for death-spirals that can be initiated with only a small, seemingly insignificant, push. Death spiral is an apt term for our models designed effect on your *DI* departments, all initiated by what appears to be a reasonable policy requirement - a small change - that could never be seen as leading to an inevitable demise. You're welcome.

[10] In regard to tenure, think about how much more nimble and agile your university could become in its competition with other universities if you removed tenure so that you could fire faculty at will. Think about the benefits of adding job precarity to the competition our scheme will initiate amongst your faculty [7]. Imposed internal competition, together with precarious job security, will get your faculty to work harder to outdo each other, so as to hold onto a job for a little longer – a sure formula to enhance your universities financial competitiveness. Not only would it up your financial competitiveness, removing tenure would also provide a new leadership tool. A tool that would allow you to suppress any dissent about new transformative measures and bold actions proposed by executive leadership. Regarding AI, using it effectively will allow you to replace the talents of overpaid faculty and staff with more efficient automated systems. There are limits, of course, in the types of talents that can be easily replaced by machines. The obvious ones, that cannot be replaced, are the talents of executive leadership.

Academic Management Primer II: All BIS Are Equal, But Some Are More Equal Than Others

notes from the front line of art-science crossover education

Adrian Lenardic, Rice Univ.; Anthony Covington, esq., 1-800-UCiteMe.

We recently published a primer for executive leaders at universities of higher education [1]. Within it, we presented a model for how leadership can remove departments they want gone while making it seem that the departments themselves are to blame. We were pleased to see how many leaders read our primer and provided valuable feedback. Along with positive comments, we got requests to make the model more in tune with the most fundamental need of leadership today.

Let us say: “Executive leaders we hear you and we are on it.”

Our model focused on the number of students a department needs to have contact with to justify its existence. We presented a way to calculate a ‘magic number’ that is just beyond the reach of departments you want gone. The number, to the outside world, appears fair and achievable. Yet it is skillfully gamed such that your loser departments cannot hit it [2]. Once those departments fall short, your only option is to cut them. No blame falls on you as the departments simply failed to step up.

A focus on student numbers follows a leadership policy that started in Great Britain and spread to Australia. It was originally referred to as “Bums-In-Seats”. Now that it has reached US shores, where we don’t hold to English words, it’s referred to as “Butts-In-Seats”. Let’s call it BIS [3]. The basic idea is that low BIS departments are not popular with your clients and are an inefficient use of your funds. Unpopular and inefficient departments have no value and need to go.

As it involves counting, BIS justified the rise of executive leadership roles to help with the counting. It also fueled a rise in consulting companies to help universities implement BIS policy [4]. That fed the economy by creating more well-paid consulting positions [5]. These are clear positives of BIS but, as leader feedback to our first model made clear, it is time to modify BIS to make it more in line with the bottom line needs you as leaders face.

Your bottom line is not about B’s (as in BIS). It’s about the value of B’s. Every B is an income unit (IU). To avoid forcing executive leadership to juggle conversions between dollars and euros and yen and crypto, let’s define a Basic Income Unit (BIU). A BIU is the monetary value of one reference under-graduate student at your university. A useful reference is an in-state student who pays full tuition [6].

With the concept of a BIU in place, we can state a truism all executive leaders should know: All BIS are created equal, but some are more equal than others. The truism follows from the fact that, at the modern neoliberal university, BIS does not equal total IUs. An example of this reality is that low-income students (LIBs), who receive university support, pay lower tuition while out of state students (OSBs) pay higher tuition, and foreign students (F\$Bs) pay even higher tuition on top of that [7].

The realities above need to go into your calculus for determining the value of a department. This moves us beyond BIS accounting.

Your focus, as a leader, is not so much on numbers of students but on the net undergraduate tuition revenue any of your departments bring in. Only in a long ago and forgotten world, where all undergraduates are valued equally, would that equate to BIS. Say it again leaders: All BIS are created equal, but some are more equal than others.

Executive leaders at airlines came to grips with the reality above. They adjusted business schemes accordingly. Airlines are inclusive as all seats are open to all, but all seats are not valued the same nor are all butts in those seats. Executive leaders of higher education can adjust, just as airline leaders have, following our BIS to BIU modified model.

Our original model can be modified to quantitatively convert our 'magic number' into a BIUs equivalent, allowing for BIU enhancements (e.g., OSB-IU or F\$B-IU) or downgrades (e.g., LIB-IU). We have done so and are happy to share [8]. For now, the qualitative adjustments you will make are as follows:

- 1) You still use our magic BIS number in public practice (better to announce a number requirement to the public as they may not be as comfortable with pricing individual students as executive leadership is [9])
- 2) When doing executive accounting, you adjust the number to a BIU metric [8]
- 3) If a low BIS department or two happens to hit a BIU requirement, you can now look like a caring leader as it will allow you to magnanimously spare a department or two (announce that you are doing that in the name of a liberal arts education)
- 4) Reward your highest BIU departments by giving them added resources for the next year while lowering resources for low BIU departments. Tell your workers (faculty and staff) that this provides needed 'incentive' for all [10]
- 5) The rewards/penalties above are not zero-sum to departments as revenue is set aside for leadership funds that allow you to adjust to changing landscapes (e.g., acquiring real estate to enhance public service within your community [11])

Leaders learn from leaders. In developing our BIS-BIU model, we learned from leaders in the airline industry [12]. The next level iteration of our model benefitted from a different leadership. A leadership that knows the value of parents. As a university leader ask yourself how much the parents of your BIUs matter to you. They often flip the bill and are willing to extend themselves to give their child the best possible experience and the greatest rewards. Keep that in mind as you read the next paragraph.

Parents know how their children can dream of going to Disneyland. The dreams lead to pressures to save for a Disneyland vacation. Parents also knows the disappointment their children can experience when they get to Disneyland and are forced to wait in long lines with the masses. That's not fair and not necessary. Leaders realized that a fairer experience would allow parents to enhance the basic experience with things like a gold pass that allows their children to skip a line or two.

This inspiration above leads to our new gold-line product: The BIS-BIU MMModel [14].

Just like tuition and leadership salaries, the working version of the MMModel doesn't come cheap [13]. We can, however, provide a tasting tour of its bold vision and excellence.

A departure point is the Bayh-Dole act. The act allows universities to profit from faculty research, via patents or ventures with start-ups [15]. Valued departments take advantage of this and should grow. Ones that cannot tap the revenue source should be downsized [16]. Accordingly, students who major in marketable departments are higher valued BIUs as they justify growth of those departments. Students who, inexplicably, choose slacker departments are calculated as downgraded BIUs (akin to an LIB-IU).

The BIU up- and down-grades come in at budgeting and at admissions. Leadership determines admissions and would-be BIUs are asked to pre-state majors. All the while a marketing narrative is provided to parents about how certain departments provide no job skills [17]. Parents will opt for the gold-line ticket adding support to your needed cuts [18]. A kicker is that F\$B-IUs tend not to apply for majors in english, philosophy, history etc. Investments in an international presence can further load those numbers [7].

The restructuring that comes from our BIU adjustments will serve leadership in political relationships, from either side of the aisle. Making higher education about job skills will: 1) Remove overly progressive, one can even say woke, fields of inquiry (e.g., ethics) from the curriculum [19]; 2) Spare students from being threatened by challenging ideas (that's not part of vocational training) and the university can become one big safe space, akin to Disneyland [20]. Depending on the political mood of the day, leaders can play up one or the other of the above (revenue opportunities will follow [11]).

Students are often given accommodations should their personal situations justify them. For example, some students need extra time for exams. Students should not be made to feel uncomfortable by having to justify their needs. Parents know best what their child's personal situation is and should be allowed a say. They are clients and deserve a seat at the table should they opt for one. Our model respects that. For a BIU up-grade, parents can get the enhanced experience of informing university leadership of a students' specific needs. That, in turn, will provide BIU justified accommodations for their child.

Leadership has already seen the value of serving clients by making sure they get the grades they deserve. Parents are paying for B's in seats not for B's on grade sheets. The downside is that companies, who hire outgoing BIUs, do not have enough time to interview all the A+ students. Our model leverages this un-intended downside in leaderships favor. For an added BIU up-grade, parents can ensure that when, for example, McKinsey & Co. or Le'GnarCov & Co. come to call, their child gets preferred seating in the interview room.

There is more to our model, but you get the gist. Our model is a logical endgame to neoliberal insights that universities best serve society by adopting a corporate worldview and business modes of operation. As university leaders you respect students and parents by valuing them as paying customers. Valued customers are entitled to an enhanced product experience should they want one.

If our model happens to benefit leadership, while removing deadweight workers, that's just customers voting with their feet (with some guidance from leaders and consulting firms). Higher education remains equitable and open to all. All are valued.

AL&AC 231222

(thanks to Leslie Chan for introducing us to the concept of a BIU)

Vintage Airline Poster Modified by Authors

Notes and References

- [1] Lenardic, A., and Covington, A. (2023). Academic Management Primer: How to Cut Departments and Come Out Blame-Free, *Future U – Neoliberalism in Higher Education*, Oct. 20, <https://futureu.education/uncategorized/academic-management-primer-how-to-cut-departments-and-come-out-blame-free/>
- [2] Our model showed how the magic number for cutting departments could be gamed to be lower than a number used by US News for University Rankings. As a leader you want to be ranked high and you know rankings favor smaller class sizes. So, you want to promote that your average class size is 20 students or less (the number used by US News). A specific example from our original primer showed how the magic cut number could, using the logic of our model, be 18 in year one and drop to 17 in year two of cuts. In effect, our model allows you to justify cuts while still promoting low class sizes. As an executive leader, you get to have your cake and eat it too. You're welcome.
- [3] As an executive leader you know, or should know, the value of using as many acronyms as possible. It signals that what you value is speed and efficiency, both in how you restructure your university and in how you communicate that to the masses (<https://www.psychologicalscience.org/observer/alienating-the-audience-how-abbreviations-hamper-scientific-communication>).
- [4] Executive leaders can't do every-thing and consulting firms, that can view the university from a detached perspective, ease the burden. There is another upside. If changes you make, as a leader, lead to negative effects (e.g., needless lay-offs without lowering of tuition), then you, as a leader, can come off blame-free (do you sense a theme?). You were only following the advice of a respected consulting firm, i.e., 'the best available advice'. Consultants are also not accountable. Consultants only give paid advice. They are not responsible for how the advice is used or if it leads to negative effects. They get paid regardless. It's the nature of being a consultant (a leader or sorts): All upside with

no skin in the game. With executive leaders and consultants free of downsides all that is left, should things go south, is to blame university workers (i.e., faculty and staff). Win-win for all leaders.

- [5] An example of how consulting fuels the economy comes from a firm that many a university leader has turned to: McKinsey & Co. From Pro-Publica: "Hiring McKinsey is a famously expensive proposition. A single junior consultant — typically a recent college or business school graduate — runs clients \$67,500 per week, or \$3.5 million annually. For \$160,000 per week, you get two consultants, the second one mid-level."
- [6] A reference tuition unit may not be the same for all universities. By allowing you to adjust the reference unit, our model lets you to make the claim that your budgeting model was designed for your university by your university. The public and your workers will eat up that personalized touch. However, aside from a reference shift, the workings of the model will be the same across all universities. That will save you the unneeded headaches of coming up with a custom plan while also allowing you to build community with leadership at other universities - doing things the same way creates a shared bond from one leader to another.
- [7] The BIU revenue you, as executive leaders, put into branding your university ties into this reality [Twitchell, J.B. (2004), Higher Ed, Inc, *The Wilson Quarterly*, 28/3, pp. 46-59, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40360871>]. Projecting an international presence also ties in (e.g., following the ivy league and ivy-adjacent policy of having a summer campus in Paris). Branding, and an international presence, is not designed to appeal so much to reference BIUs. Rather, it's part of the strategy to attract out of state and, more ideally, out of country students whose value comes with a BIU enhancement factor.
- [8] In our first primer, we provided our entry level model for free. That was a sign of how much we care about higher education. That said, you can't expect excellence for free. After all, that's what you, as leaders, tell your clients when tuitions rise. Our taster model showed how much more excellent we are than other consulting firms. Providing it for free showed how bold we are (bold is an excellent branding word). Our boldness and excellence led leaders like yourself to invest in Le'GnarCov & Co. We are now ready to satisfy your leadership needs. Simply send Leader Lenardic or Leader Covington a request for pricing quotes on algorithms to convert our entry model to a BIS-BIU model.
- [9] There is historical precedence to confirm this. See, for example, *A Modest Proposal* by Jonathan Swift (<https://www.gutenberg.org/files/1080/1080-h/1080-h.htm>)
- [10] Enforced competition between workers is a way to build comradery while squeezing out low revenue departments (survivors of budget games will have a shared bond). As leaders you are removed from the competitive accountability. It would be unfair to blame you if university value drops. The blame for that would be with workers who mis-applied and/or mis-interpreted your newly imposed policies.
- [11] Baldwin, D.L. (2021). *In the Shadow of the Ivory Tower: How Universities Are Plundering Our Cities*, New York: Bold Type Books.
- [12] As a leader, it is a good strategy when talking to clients, workers, or the public, to stress how many other leaders you talk to. A good example would be to preface any changes

you impose with “After discussions with city leaders in politics, business and entrepreneurship, we have decided that the best path forward is to ...”

- [13] As leaders, you know it should not come cheap. You set your tuitions to be at the level of universities you aspire too, no matter how high, as a signal to parents that you are of equal value. Imagine the tarnish to your brand if you offered lower tuition. We all know ‘you get what you pay for’ and ‘cheap is cheap’ (one can even add that ‘perception is reality’). The signal that our MMModel is better than what you get from other consulting firms is its higher price [5]. Trust us, you’ll get what you pay for.
- [14] The model is, indeed, named after a certain mouse. Adding some whimsy to your’ leader-speak can go a long way, especially with nostalgic parents.
- [15] This comes with two added bonuses: 1) Universities are still viewed as serving the public good when it comes to tax purposes; 2) Many of the research ideas that allow for privatization where originally funded by government grants (i.e., by public tax dollars). See, for example: Lenardic, A. (2023). Innovation at University, Inc., *Future U – Neoliberalism in Higher Education*, Sept. 2, <https://futureu.education/higher-ed/commentary-by-adrian-lenardic-innovation-at-university-inc/>
- [16] Patents rarely come from history departments and eager start-ups aren’t knocking on philosophy department doors. Engineering and business departments, on the other hand, produce marketable ideas that can be sold back to the public (even as you maintain non-profit status).
- [17] Blackwood, S. (2023). Letter from an English Department on the Brink, *The New York Review*, April 2, <https://www.nybooks.com/online/2023/04/02/letter-from-an-english-department-on-the-brink/>
- [18] Parents will also see that some majors, with the enhanced educational rewards they offer, should come with a higher effective BIU entry fee. Tuitions can still rise even as low BIU departments are cut in the name of reduced costs (e.g., leadership discretionary funds need to grow as cuts are made; good leaders, who save money by cutting departments, become more valued and salaries must rise to reflect that). For this reason, it’s important to maintain a marketing strategy that reassures parents that rising tuitions reflect added value – you get what you pay for [13].
- [19] Snyder, C.A. (2023). A Liberal Education in Name Only, *Inside Higher Ed*, Oct 23, <https://www.insidehighered.com/opinion/views/2023/10/23/liberal-education-name-only-opinion>
- [20] Lukianoff, G., & Haidt, J. (2018). *The Coddling of the American Mind*, New York: Penguin Press.

After the Fact

The following notes were added after the main two essays in the Academic Primer Diptych were finished and had been posted on Future U. The links to the Future U versions:

<https://futureu.education/uncategorized/academic-management-primer-how-to-cut-departments-and-come-out-blame-free/>

and

<https://futureu.education/perspectives/commentary-academic-management-primer-ii-all-bis-are-equal-but-some-are-more-equal-than-others/>

Hopefully this won't come as a shock, but the Primers were intended as Swifitean Parodies, ala *A Modest Proposal For preventing the Children of Poor People From being a Burthen to Their Parents or Country, and For making them Beneficial to the Publick* -

<https://www.gutenberg.org/files/1080/1080-h/1080-h.htm>

Seems Parody can't keep up with the reality University Leadership is creating ... A recent move by an Australian Uni made this ever so clear and amusingly our second primer noted how many 'innovations' start in the UK/Australia and then come to the US, so get ready if you're at a US University because this is likely heading your way.

When we proposed the Airline-Disneyland student upgrade model with perks of being first to interview with McKinsey and Co etc., we had our tongues in cheek thinking we may have pushed parody into the silly realm but ... well here we are:

<https://www.adelaide.edu.au/the-academy/>

The Academy (announced in the link above) comes with enhanced fees above regular tuition for students and in return Deloitte (a consulting firm) will "pick" from that pool of students for jobs after graduation. It provides a way for BIUs (still referred to as Students in university brochures) to upgrade their educational experience. The gold line pass that comes with enhanced perks.

The big consulting companies aren't shy about telling you how they want to commodify education:

<https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/ca/Documents/human-capital/ca-en-human-capital-higher-education-evolving.pdf>

and

<https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/education/our-insights/how-to-transform-higher-education-institutions-for-the-long-term>

The hits, as they say, keep coming.

In yet more in the "you can't make this up" and "parody is now reality" vein:

<https://www.chron.com/news/houston-texas/education/article/rice-university-financial-aid-18617028.php>

Too many LIBs will lower a university's overall BIUs, as our Academic Leadership Model shows. Executive leadership can't have that (easier to pay legal fees).

Some insights from John Oliver about a consulting firm that has been hired by many an academic leader to help make universities more efficient. Enjoy.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AiOUoVd6xQ>

“Academia is a serious place, and it takes itself seriously. But it is also, like Hollywood or Washington, profoundly ridiculous ... (and) can only really be understood through satire.”

- A.O. Scott in New York Times Book Review (Feb 25, 2024).

A nice post by John Traphagen on quantocrats and such:

<https://futureu.education/education/commentary-the-rubricization-of-higher-education-implications-and-consequences/>

University damage control brought to you by Dell Technologies and Google ChromeOS. The vid below is longer than you need to watch but the opening and the credits below give the gist:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1d41qzYFJAU>

No worries about corporate capture here, right? The spin that its "all about the student experience" is great parody (being pitched as reality) - it almost reads like something we could have included in our primer:

"And remember leaders, when you get challenged for making needless and inhumane cuts, make sure to say: 'it's all about the student experience.'"

Here's a recent Instagram post from my own universities PR department.

The telling line: "... opportunities for employees to participate with university leaders ..."

At least the powers that be in the C-Suites are now being completely honest and have dropped all pretense that the rest of us should aspire to be 'team players.'

The corporatization of universities was never about a team to begin with. It comes down to leaders or employees. If you're not a leader, you're just another employee.

But hey, leadership is still willing to fraternize with you a bit by offering 'many opportunities to participate with them in different ways.' None of the ways seem to involve participating in discussions of how a university should function or what the purpose of higher education should be or what a fair breakout of salaries is amongst executive university leaders versus all those in-the-trenches employees, who it seems are unwell and in need of a Wellness Wednesday.